

Grievance Handling Procedure in an Indian Sugar Industry: Outcome and Sustainability

¹Dr. Anupama Nalkurti, ²Prof.G.L.Narayanappa

I. Introduction

'JUPITER' sugars India LTD was founded in 1941 in southern India as a private sugar factory. Later it enhanced its production from 1000 TCD to 8500 TCD in the year 1962. It was amalgamating many subunits and multi locational products into its main unit. The company has focused its attention on various projects and substantial resources. Subsequently, they have decided to organize the company into two units one in southern India and one in northern India.

Sugar industry is one of the most important agro-based industries in India and is extremely accountable for creating a major impact on rural economy in particular and the country's economy in broad-spectrum. Sugar has been yield in the Indian subcontinent since ancient times and then it spread to other parts of the world¹. Sugarcane is a native of tropical Indian subcontinent and Southeast Asia. Sugar industry ranks second amongst major agro-based industries in India. In India, sugarcane is planted thrice a year in October, March and July depending on part of the country. The majority of the sugar production in India takes at local Cooperative Sugar mills². After Independence, India made serious plans for overall industrial development of sugar industry³.

The Indian sugar industry is independent in its energy needs and further makes additional exportable power through cogeneration. The different byproducts of sugar industry likewise add to the economic development of the nation to advancing various additional industries. Sugarcane has developed as a multi-product crop utilized as an essential raw material for the manufacture of sugar, ethanol, paper, electricity and besides a cogeneration of subsidiary product. The taking care of dairy cattle of sugarcane is a significant source of bio-vitality and more demand in rural areas. Molasses is an essential sustain stock for distilleries. The ethanol necessity of the nation is going up progressively.

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1. Academic Consultant, Department of Management, Dravidian University, Kuppam.
 2. Dean, School of Commerce and Management, Dravidian University, Kuppam.

In the sugar industry, creation of power utilizing biogases was the typical option and utilization of biogases as a substitute raw material for wood pulp for monetary and ecological sustainability

Importance of Grievance Handling Procedure

Grievance is an issue raised by worker to utter dissatisfaction with management behaviour and is an endeavour to fetch out changes (D'Cruz, 1999)⁴. A grievance is caused because of the distinction between the representatives' desires and administrative practices. Grievances may because of a few causes like contrasts of feeling, poor working conditions, questions and fears, compensation, supervision, infringement of collective bargaining and so forth. The employers likewise may have grievances against their workers because of indiscipline, less yield, less quality, collective bargaining understandings, reckless disposition of trade union leaders, and such.

DEALING OF GRIEVANCES

Employers embrace various approaches to deal with grievance handling machinery relies on different variables including the attitude of board and workers. Incredibly in the Indian context administrations are more progressively liable to be legalistic approach in view of the broad impact of the legal framework on industrial relations. Moreover,

numerous administrations follow a human relations approach towards their labourers. Frequently, they likewise follow an open-door and step-ladder approach in this regard⁵.

The three approaches with respect to the disposition of board and employees of handling of grievance are:

1. Legalistic View Approach
2. Human Relations Approach
3. Open-Door or Step-Ladder Approach

LEGALISTIC VIEW APPROACH

Administrations following legalistic approach regularly refer to the negotiated contract when a worker raises a complaint or grievance. They contend that the circumstance has been deal with in the negotiated contact. The management and the employee follow the provisions in that. Grievances are those characterized by the agreement, and the procedure for dealing with the grievances is obvious to all concerned and determined with the time span for each stage. The impact of the supervisor approach in recognizing the issue of grievance and the principles ought to be set up so that managers are coordinated by their prevalent⁶.

HUMAN RELATIONS APPROACH

The premise of the development of this philosophy is human relations school. The worker and his particular issue is the significant concern. The manager thoughtfully tunes into the grievances in an expert way in order to enable the person overcome his concern, the basic assumption being that workers are a higher priority than productions targets. Almost certainly understanding their needs and grievances will help in achieving production targets, yet principally workers are the end rather than a means to end. "The capacity to be an attentive listener is too frequently taken for settled. HR professionals play crucial role in the organization. They infuse an emotion of confidence and conviction among the staff members by listening and settling their issues and concerns. Employee grievances are basically human issues, genuine or fanciful"⁷.

OPEN -DOOR AND STEP-LADDER APPROACH

Channels of handling grievances ought to painstakingly evolve and its data should be spread among the representatives. It is fundamental that workers know the channels through which they ventilate their grievance. The two methods for redressal of grievances are open door-policy or step-ladder procedure.

In step-ladder procedure, an aggrieved worker will initially move toward the line manager with his grievance. In the event that he doesn't fulfill with the decision of the manager, he moves toward the head of department, the subsequent level, with his grievance. At the third level, a joint grievance committee audits the grievance. On the off chance that the grievance is as yet not settled, it is additionally eluded to the chief executive of the organization.

In all the above mentioned methods, the designations of authorities to whom the grievance are presented, the time allotment for the removal of grievances at each progression, the way where the grievances must be presented, verbally or in writing or an ordinary paper or on prescribed is presented with their concern.

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Select Review of Literature

Wyman (1971)⁸ proposed that "executives must give a composed solution regarding grievance resolution outcome to troubled subordinate". He additionally coded that unlike oral responses to spoken grievances, the written answer should adjust to established protocol which comes down from the management. Furthermore, system declares that the written grievance must be shaved of every other impinging feature however pervasive and controlling. A printed answer for grievance management is required as a record for instance case if the same issue emerges in future. The need for recorded grievance resolution result also needed if the grievance is mentioned to the next step in grievance procedure (Industrial Harmony Code for Conduct, n.d).

Gordon and Miller (1984)⁹ states that the studies the influence of the supervisors" approach in identifying the issue of grievance It is also cited that the rules should be set up so that supervisors are directed by their predominant

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Margolies, K. (2004)¹⁰ In the book of, "Strategic grievance handling" express the change between dissatisfaction, grievance and complaint. Discontent raises when an individual is not happy in his job and when the organization does not recognise the individual goals. This dissatisfaction prompts to grievances when an individual talks about it with the other employee in the organization. At the point when the dissatisfaction related to the work is brought to the declaration of the management, complaint becomes a grievance.

MohanaSundaram.V. andSaranya.N (2013)¹¹ in their article entitled "Employee Grievance" organizations are made up of peoples and functions through people. Without people organizations cannot exist. The resources of men, money, material and machinery are collected, coordinated and utilized through people in the organizations. It is through the combined efforts of people that the materials and monetary resources are effectively utilized for the attainment of common objectives and goals without unity of human efforts no organization can achieve its goals.

Balamurugan.G and Shenbagapandian.V (2016)¹² have opined that the administration should ensure that the grievances should be stable promptly, so that the workers get the necessary intelligence of satisfaction. As former stated, Redressal of the grievances is a must to preserve good labour management relations and industrial peace. Thus, the management should certify that the grievance should be received and settled promptly, so that the workers get the essential sense of satisfaction. The distressed employee approaches the front line supervisor first. If the concern is unionized, a representative of trade union also links the supervisor in handling the grievance. All the grievances cannot be resolved in this step, as these may be beyond the authority and competence of the manager. In the next step, the mid-level manager, generally the personnel officer, along with a mid-union officer attempt to tackle the grievance. In the third step, the top administration and top union leaders be seated together to settle grievances concerning companywide issued. If the grievance keeps on unsettled, it is referred to an external arbitrator for Redressal.

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is confined to the procedure of collective bargaining in management in 'JUPITER' sugars India Ltd. Only. The outcomes of this study cannot be generalized to any other company.

Objectives

The specific objectives of this paper are

- i. To assess the contemporary patterns of grievance handling procedure in 'JUPITER' Sugars India Limited;
- ii. To measure the level of satisfaction/dissatisfaction of employees/workers towards the contemporary patterns of grievance handling procedure in 'JUPITER' Sugars India Limited;
- iii. To identify the reasons for the dissatisfaction of employees/workers respondents towards the contemporary pattern of grievance handling procedure in 'JUPITER' Sugars India Limited;
- iv. To offer the feasible ways and means to streamline the contemporary patterns of grievance handling procedure in 'JUPITER' Sugars India Limited.

II. Research Methodology

The methodology consists of data collection from primary as well as secondary source. Through the survey method, the firsthand information was collected from 60 sample respondents from the study unit.

Sample design and size

A purposive-cum-convenient sampling technique was followed and 60 respondents were chosen as sample respondents from the study unit.

Analysis of the data

The information collected from the sample respondents was processed and tabulated scientifically and several statistical tools like (i) independent sample t-test; (ii) weighted mean scores; and (iii) ANOVA are calculated at appropriate levels.

The Limitations

1. The study is confined to only one sugar unit;
2. The size of the sample is 60 only where the number is very meagre.

Research findings

1. Both the management or the management representatives are not able to properly understand the grievances of employees/workers and hence There would be big gap in the understanding level of the grievances of workers. (38.33%)
2. The designated officials for whom the management appointed for handling grievances are not positively appraising the employees grievances to the management not and hence the grievance are not able to be redressed positively on time. (26.66 %)
3. The management/management's representatives who are designated for redressing the grievance are not directly discussing the grievances with aggrieved employees/workers. They are discussing with section heads or union leaders. Hence, the reality of the grievance and gravity of the situation are not properly realized and redressed. (21.66%)
4. 100 percent of the grievances are not redressed. For Ex: a worker/employee is having grievance related to his wages and service matters. When the issue of this worker is presented in grievance handling procedure his wage matter is only attending and the service matter is post pond. Hence the grievances are accumulating. (11.66%)

Suggestions

1. The management or the representatives of management should properly understand the grievances of the employees sympathetically. Further, they should have positive attitude towards the redressal of the employee's grievances. So that the functional distance between the employees and the management can be wiped out.
2. While undertaking the process of grievance handling mechanism, the concerned officials or the representatives of the management should positively appraise the work performance, caliber and characteristics of the concerned employees whose matters are discussing in the collective bargaining process. So that the concerned officials will have positive attitude on the grievances of the employees and they can sympathetically consider their grievances and find out reasonable solutions for the same.
3. Further, the designated officers who are designated for redressing the grievances should directly address the aggrieved employees and extract the first hand information regarding the grievance. So the factual information related to the grievance can be elicited and suitable solutions for the grievances can be suggested. If these designated officers discusses with union leaders or any personnel who are not connected with grievance, false information would enter into the grievance redressal process and the entire process would become trash. So that the contacting of union leaders and other officials in connection with the information about a particular employee should be avoided.
4. The proposed grievance committee constituted by the company should totally (100%) address the grievance and find out the suitable remedies for the maladies. At any cost partial redressal of the grievance should not be carried out. In this regard it is also stated that the partial redressal of the grievance, instead of getting the social change into the organization it increases the unrest in to the minds of aggrieved employees and the quantum of grievances would also be increased. Hence, it is suggested that 100 percent of the grievances should be addressed without giving any scope for the frustration of the aggrieved employees.

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